

EFFECT OF CERAMIC LAYER THICKNESS AND TEMPERATURE ON MECHANICAL STRESS IN Al/TiB₂ AND Ti/SiO₂ MICROLAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The dependence of mechanical stress on temperature and ceramic layer thickness is examined in Al/TiB₂ and Ti/SiO₂ multilayers. Annealing of as deposited Al/TiB₂ microlaminates at 400 °C produces a dramatic change in the sign and magnitude of the average stress. As the TiB₂ layer thickness is increased, the stress in annealed Al/TiB₂ microlaminates goes through a maximum. In contrast, the stress in the Ti/SiO₂ system decreases monotonically, as the SiO₂ layer thickness is increased. Annealed Al/TiB₂ microlaminates display tensile stresses and pure elastic deformation in the 25 - 400 °C range. In the same temperature range, tensile stresses and plastic deformation of Ti were observed in Ti/SiO₂ microlaminates with thin SiO₂ layers.

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic fiber - metal matrix composites are advanced structural materials that exhibit potential for high strength / high temperature applications. The mechanical behavior of metal-matrix composites can obviously be influenced by the volume fraction of ceramic constituent. The addition of 15% SiC particulate reinforcement to a bulk Al alloy produces a substantial increase in the yield stress and only a small increase in the elastic modulus[1]. Room temperature mechanical testing experiments showed that the ultimate tensile strength of a Zn-Al alloy matrix composite decreased almost linearly with the addition of alumina fibers, but the hardness and fatigue life of the composites increased with an increase in fiber volume[2]. In thin film microlaminates, the volume fraction of ceramic constituent can be varied simply by changing the thickness of the ceramic layers. In ceramic (TiN) - ceramic (TiB₂) microlaminates[3], the hardness measured by a nanoindenter increased initially and then decreased as the thickness of TiB₂ layers increased from 300 Å to 2400 Å. Weihs et al[4] found that the hardness generally increased with the volume fraction of the Cu-Zr phase in Cu/Cu-Zr multilayer foils. The hardnesses were determined to be high and the dependence of hardness on the volume fraction was stronger, when the films were loaded parallel to the layers as compared to loading normal to the layers. Significant changes in the sign and magnitude of stress were observed in single thin metallic layers[5], single ceramic layers[6], and thin film metal/ceramic (Al/SiC) microlaminates[6], when as deposited samples were heated at 400 °C for an hour. In most instances, a reversal from compressive to tensile stress was observed. When a force is applied parallel to the layering in a 3-D laminated composite, iso-strain condition exist[7]. Under this condition, a volume fraction rule (simple rule of mixtures) applies to quantities such as stress, modulus, and hardness. Also, in the theoretical treatment of thin film multilayers, a simple rule of mixtures has been assumed for the curvature change of the substrate[8]. The curvature change of the substrate for a multilayer can be given by the sum of the curvature changes contributed from each single layer present in the multilayer assembly. The hardness of Cu/Cu-Zr multilayer foils was found to follow a simple rule of mixtures, when the loading was carried out in directions parallel and normal to their layering[4]. The purpose of the present work is to study the effect of

ceramic layer thickness and temperature on thin film stress in Al/TiB₂ and Ti/SiO₂ microlaminates and to find out whether a simple rule of mixtures exists for the substrate curvature and for the curvature change with temperature.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Al/TiB₂ and Ti/SiO₂ microlaminates were prepared by depositing alternately the metallic (Al or Ti) and ceramic layers (TiB₂ or SiO₂) layers in a Vac-Tec model 250 Batch Side sputtering system. Al, Ti, and TiB₂ layers were dc magnetron sputtered and SiO₂ layers were rf magnetron sputtered. Deposition was carried out on 2" oxidized Si wafers for stress measurement and on small strips of the same substrate material for determination of structure. Sputtering conditions for the deposition of Al were 400 W, 5 mTorr Ar; for Ti 600 W, 5 mTorr Ar; for TiB₂ 400 W, 5 mTorr Ar; and for SiO₂ 600 W, 20 mTorr Ar. Base pressure in the sputtering chamber was 6x10⁻⁷ torr. Single Al, Ti, TiB₂ and SiO₂ layers with different thicknesses were also deposited for comparison purposes. The details of single layer and multilayer samples prepared in this study are listed in Table 1. Film thicknesses and deposition rates were estimated using a Dektak-IIa surface profilometer. Annealing of Al films was carried out in a furnace at 1x10⁻⁷ torr pressure for 1 hour at 400 °C. Microlaminates and other single layers were annealed at the same temperature in flowing Ar gas at atmospheric pressure. A Rigaku D/MAX-2BX X-ray diffractometer with Cu K α radiation was used to determine the structure of layers present in the microlaminates. A Flexus 2320 thin film stress measurement system with in-situ heating facilities was used to determine the stress at room temperature and as a function of temperature.

Table 1. Description of single layer and microlaminate samples.

Sample	Thickness
Single Al layers	240 - 3800 Å
Single Ti Layers	2700 - 21200 Å
Single TiB ₂ layers	200 - 5000 Å
Single SiO ₂ layers	1800 - 28000 Å
(300 Å Al / t _{TiB₂} TiB ₂) _n t _{TiB₂} = thickness of TiB ₂ layers n = number of bilayers	t _{TiB₂} = 50 Å, n=9 t _{TiB₂} = 150 Å, n=7 t _{TiB₂} = 300 Å, n=5 t _{TiB₂} = 800 Å, n=3 t _{TiB₂} = 1500 Å, n=2
(5300 Å Ti / t _{SiO₂} SiO ₂) ₆ t _{SiO₂} = thickness of SiO ₂ layers number of bilayers = 6	t _{SiO₂} = 1800 Å t _{SiO₂} = 3700 Å t _{SiO₂} = 7400 Å t _{SiO₂} = 14700 Å

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Structure:

X-ray diffraction (XRD) studies indicate that all of the Al layers and TiB₂ layers with thicknesses less than 900 Å are random polycrystalline. Hexagonal basal plane texture was observed in Ti layers of all thicknesses and in TiB₂ layers with thicknesses greater than 900 Å.

All of the SiO_2 layers exhibit broad, amorphous peaks. Representative XRD scans of a $(300 \text{ \AA} \text{ Al} / 1500 \text{ \AA} \text{ TiB}_2)_2$ microlaminate and a $(5300 \text{ \AA} \text{ Ti} / 7400 \text{ \AA} \text{ SiO}_2)_6$ microlaminate annealed at 400°C are shown in Figs. 1 (a) & (b), respectively.

Figure 1. XRD scans of (a) a $(300 \text{ \AA} \text{ Al} / 1500 \text{ \AA} \text{ TiB}_2)_2$ microlaminate and (b) a $(5300 \text{ \AA} \text{ Ti} / 7400 \text{ \AA} \text{ SiO}_2)_6$ microlaminate annealed at 400°C .

2. Room Temperature Stress:

The average film stress determined for single layers as a function of film thickness at room temperature is presented in Figs. 2 (a), (b), (c), and (d). It is clearly seen that the stress moves in the tensile direction, for all the materials, when the films were annealed at 400°C . Significant changes in stress with film thickness were observed for Al, Ti, and TiB_2 layers, however stress was almost constant with film thickness for SiO_2 layers. Also, the stress in SiO_2 layers remained compressive, even after annealing at 400°C . The change in stress with annealing can be attributed to phenomena such as film densification, annihilation of defects associated with sputtering, and grain growth.

The dependence of average stress on ceramic layer thickness (TiB_2 or SiO_2) in as deposited and annealed Al/ TiB_2 and Ti/ SiO_2 microlaminates is presented in Figs. 3(a) and 3(b), respectively. The stress values for microlaminates generally fall between the values of the constituent single layers except for a couple of Al/ TiB_2 microlaminates. Very large changes in stress in Al/ TiB_2 microlaminates were found for all Al/ TiB_2 microlaminates with annealing. Stress in annealed Al/ TiB_2 microlaminates goes through a maximum, as the thickness of TiB_2 is varied from 50 \AA to 1500 \AA despite the fact that the annealed stress systematically decreases with increasing TiB_2 thickness in single TiB_2 layers. Change in stress for Ti/ SiO_2 microlaminates with annealing is smaller and decreases with increasing SiO_2 layer thickness. Both as deposited stress and annealed stress decrease gradually with SiO_2 layer thickness. However, the stress in single SiO_2 layers is almost constant with film thickness.

Figure 2. Single layer film stress as a function of film thickness (a) Al (b) Ti (c) TiB₂ and (d) SiO₂.

Figure 3. Film stress as a function of (a) TiB₂ layer thickness in Al/TiB₂ microlaminates (b) SiO₂ layer thickness in Ti/SiO₂ microlaminates.

It is surprising to note that annealed stress is a smooth function of ceramic layer thickness, when data from both microlaminate systems are plotted together (Fig. 4), even though the composition and thickness of the layers are very different.

Figure 4. Effect of ceramic layer thickness (t_{TiB_2} or t_{SiO_2}) on the average stress in annealed $(300 \text{ \AA} \text{ Al} / t_{TiB_2} \text{ TiB}_2)_n$ and $(5300 \text{ \AA} \text{ Ti} / t_{SiO_2} \text{ SiO}_2)_6$ microlaminates.

The average stress in annealed Al/TiB₂ and Ti/SiO₂ microlaminates is plotted in Fig. 5 as a function of the volume fraction of the ceramic constituent (V_{SiO_2} or V_{TiB_2}). The stress in annealed Ti/SiO₂ microlaminates depends linearly on volume fraction of SiO₂ and follows a volume-fraction rule (or a simple rule of mixtures).

Figure 5. Stress in annealed Al/TiB₂ and Ti/SiO₂ microlaminates as a function of volume fraction of TiB₂ (or SiO₂).

3. Stress - Temperature Behavior:

Stress - Temperature diagrams determined for $(5300 \text{ \AA} \text{ Ti} / t_{SiO_2} \text{ SiO}_2)$ microlaminates with several t_{SiO_2} values are presented in Fig. 6. Microlaminates with $t_{SiO_2} = 1800 \text{ \AA}$ and 3700 \AA are in tension over the temperature range of 25 - 400 °C, while the microlaminates with $t_{SiO_2} = 7400 \text{ \AA}$ and 14700 \AA are in compression. The Ti layers undergo plastic deformation in tension for microlaminates with thin SiO₂ layers. The stress - temperature slope in the tensile elastic region, $-d\sigma/dT$, decreases with an increase in t_{SiO_2} . In comparison, all of the single SiO₂ layers predominantly are in compression from 25 °C to 400 °C, while the 5300 Å Ti layer is in tension in the same temperature range. The stress - temperature slope for single SiO₂ layers is independent of film thickness. Al/TiB₂ microlaminates display predominantly tensile stresses for all TiB₂ thicknesses and showed only elastic deformation from 25 °C to 400 °C (Fig. 7). The

Figure 6. Stress -Temperature diagrams determined for annealed $(5300 \text{ \AA Ti} / t_{\text{SiO}_2} \text{ SiO}_2)_6$ microlaminates.

Figure 7. Stress-temperature diagrams determined for annealed $(300 \text{ \AA Al} / t_{\text{TiB}_2} \text{ TiB}_2)_n$ microlaminates.

elastic slope, $-d\sigma/dT$, determined for Al/TiB₂ microlaminates is found to be essentially independent of TiB₂ layer thickness similar to the case of single TiB₂ layers. The slope of the stress-temperature curve in the elastic region, $-d\sigma/dt$, for a single or multilayer thin film system equals the product $(E \cdot \Delta\alpha)$ of the biaxial modulus (E) of the film and the difference in thermal

expansion coefficients ($\Delta\alpha$) of the film and substrate material. Since the increase in SiO_2 layer thickness decreases both the modulus and thermal expansion coefficient of Ti/SiO_2 microlaminate composite (a volume-fraction rule was assumed to estimate modulus and thermal expansion coefficient), the slope, $-\text{d}\sigma/\text{d}T$, decreases with an increase in t_{SiO_2} . On the other hand, increasing the TiB_2 layer thickness increases the modulus but decreases the thermal expansion coefficient of Al/TiB_2 microlaminates. Therefore, because of the offsetting effects, the slope, $-\text{d}\sigma/\text{d}T$, remains almost constant with t_{TiB_2} . Even though Al has a lower yield strength both in compression and tension when compared to Ti, plastic deformation was observed only for Ti in the corresponding microlaminates. The enhanced strengthening effect observed in Al/TiB_2 microlaminates may be accounted for by a combination of factors, namely, smaller layer thicknesses and the presence of a stronger ceramic layer, TiB_2 . In both microlaminate systems, stress values for 25 - 400 °C fall between the values for single layers in the same temperature range.

4. Rule of mixtures calculations:

Calculations were performed to determine whether the substrate curvature and change in curvature with temperature follows a simple rule of mixtures. The measured curvature change of the substrate due to the deposition of the microlaminate has been compared (Fig. 8(a) for the Al/TiB_2 system and Fig. 8(b) for the Ti/SiO_2 system) to the calculated sum of the curvature changes measured due to the independent deposition of each layer present in the microlaminate.

Figure 8. Substrate curvature change as a function of (a) TiB_2 layer thickness in Al/TiB_2 microlaminates (b) SiO_2 layer thickness in Ti/SiO_2 microlaminates.

In both systems, the measured curvature values are close to the calculated sums in as deposited and annealed states at low ceramic layer thicknesses. Significant discrepancies were found at high ceramic layer thicknesses except in an annealed $(300 \text{ \AA Al} / 1500 \text{ \AA TiB}_2)_2$ microlaminate. It is also observed from Figs. 9 (a) and (b) that the measured substrate curvature change with temperature for the microlaminates exhibits the same trends and reasonably agrees with the calculated sum obtained from experiments performed on single layers except for the case of a $(5300 \text{ \AA Ti} / 14700 \text{ \AA SiO}_2)_6$ microlaminate.

Figure 9. Slope of curvature change with temperature as a function of (a) TiB_2 layer thickness in annealed Al/TiB_2 microlaminates and (b) SiO_2 layer thickness in annealed Ti/SiO_2 microlaminates.

CONCLUSIONS

The average stress in as deposited and annealed microlaminates generally lies between the values of the constituent single layers with two exceptions $(300 \text{ \AA Al} / 150 \text{ \AA TiB}_2)_7$, and $(300 \text{ \AA Al} / 300 \text{ \AA TiB}_2)_5$. On annealing at $400 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the stress in Al/TiB_2 microlaminates changed to high tensile values. In the Ti/SiO_2 system, small changes in stress are observed in microlaminates with thin SiO_2 layers. As the thickness of TiB_2 layers is increased from 50 \AA to 1500 \AA , the stress initially increases and then decreases. On the other hand, the stress in Ti/SiO_2 microlaminates decreases gradually with the thickness of SiO_2 layers. All of the Al/TiB_2 microlaminates and Ti/SiO_2 microlaminates containing thin SiO_2 layers predominantly are in the tensile stress regime in the $25\text{-}400 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ range. Ti layers deform plastically under tension in Ti/SiO_2 microlaminates with thin SiO_2 layers. Al/TiB_2 microlaminates showed only elastic deformation. A simple rule of mixtures applies for the substrate curvature in as deposited and annealed microlaminates with thin ceramic layers and for the change in curvature with temperature for most of the annealed microlaminates.

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